

Recovering metals and mineral fraction
from steelmaking residues

Deliverable 1.1

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Project details

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Abbreviations and acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
TC	Technical Committee
WP	Workpackage
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ORD	Open Research Data
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
tbd	To be declared (will be updated in future versions)
CE	Circular Economy
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package

Abstract

The present document aims to support partners in the effective and efficient administration, procedural and financial management of the project. The consortium partners will follow all the procedures included in this deliverable in order to ensure a coherent and robust management of ReMFra activities, where the governance structure will play a key role.

The present deliverable includes useful information to guarantee the good development of the project. This refers to:

- a) General Data
- b) Governance Structure
- c) Communication procedures and tools
- d) Quality control
- e) Risk analysis and management
- f) Project reporting

This deliverable will support all project partners in order to follow the statements agreed, moreover being able to use the appropriate communication channels and addressing the specific person/s depending on the scope of the activity.

1 Introduction

The ReMFra project handbook has been prepared to guide project participants through all aspects of the project's management and coordination activities. This document sets the basis of the governance structure, the communication channels and methods and the periodicity of the reporting to the task and WP leaders, the Project Coordinator and the European Commission.

1.1 Project Summary

Each year, the EU steel sector generates several million tons of metal and mineral containing residues that are currently largely under-exploited and often sent to landfills with an enormous waste of resources that could replace virgin materials. ReMFra main objective is the development and validation of a highly efficient pyrometallurgic melting and reduction demonstration plant at relevant industrial scale for recovering metals and minerals contained in a wide range of steelmaking residues.

The ReMFra process will allow to valorise steelmaking residues, such as filter dust, scale, sludge and slags, to obtain pig iron, iron rich oxides, a highly concentrated zinc oxide and an inert slag. ReMFra comprises two main parts to be developed, improved and tested at industrial scale: Plasma Reactor and RecoDust. The first will be dedicated to recover the coarse residues (scale, sludge, slag), while the second will focus on fine-grained dusts. The project will allow the improvement of iron yield using recovered pig iron instead of new pig iron and replacing the iron ore with the iron rich oxide. The recovery of concentrated ZnO and inert slag as by-products will provide a significant source of income and will contribute to the overall carbon neutrality. To reach the full circularity, the process foresees the use, as reducing agent, of secondary carbon sources (i.e. waste plastics). Energy recovery solutions will also be integrated in the metal recovery process starting from enabling the use of molten pig iron.

ReMFra is expected not only to enable technological advances in the demonstrators involved but will also contribute to the development of new standards, training programmes, adaptation and certification of industrial processes thus facilitating the replication of the project.

2 Governance structure

ReMFra project will be carried out by an interdisciplinary and well-balanced consortium with large experience in the steel sector. Six different countries are represented (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, and Spain), ensuring wide dissemination of project results and replication of solutions proposed (most of the companies have affiliates in the whole Europe). The consortium involves 5 large companies (steel producers), 1 university, 4 RTOs and 1 European Technology Platform, with an adequate budget and access to the infrastructure required to perform their activities, guaranteeing that all the WPs are optimally covered without overlapping in the different tasks.

Figure 1: Governance structure of ReMFra and WP leaders

DALMINE will be the Project Coordinator (PC), acting as main contact with the EC and chairing the General Assembly (GA) (decision-making body) and Steering Committee (SC) (execution body).

Work Package Leaders (WPL) and Task Leaders (TL) are responsible for the overall management and coordination at WP and task level and the achievement of the defined results.

2.1 Project Coordinator

- Responsible partner: DALMINE, represented by Mr. Fabio Praolini.
- Reporting to: European Commission.

The coordinator will play the role of the interlocutor of ReMFra project and will be the contact point for the EC. The Project Coordinator will chair the General Assembly and the Steering Committee.

In particular, the Project Coordinator will be responsible for:

- Supervision of project progress and assuring the effective achievement of the ReMFra implementation plan
- Contact point with the EC, as well as networking with other European/national related initiatives and projects
- Reception and distribution amongst partners of EC contribution
- Definition of project communication flows, tools and methods
- Maintenance of the Consortium Agreement
- Responsible for the collection of partner progress and financial reports and preparation of related reports to the EC, as well as submission of project deliverables to the EC.
- Oversees the awareness, dissemination and training plans and their deployment.
- Monitoring compliance by the partners with their obligations.
- Keeping the address list of contacts and other contact persons updated and available.
- Collecting, reviewing and submitting information on the progress of the Project, reports and other deliverables to the EC.
- Preparing the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing the agenda of GA meetings, chairing the meetings, preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings.
- Transmitting promptly documents and information connected with the Project to the partners and to the EC in accordance with the terms of the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement.

If one or more of the partners is late in submission of any project deliverable, the Coordinator may nevertheless submit the other partners' project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the EC in time.

If the PC fails in its coordination tasks, the GA may propose to the EC to change the Coordinator.

The PC shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party or of the consortium, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the Grant Agreement or this Consortium Agreement.

The Coordinator shall not enlarge its role beyond the tasks specified in this CA and in the GA.

2.2 General Assembly

- Chaired by: DALMINE, represented by Mr. Fabio Praolini
- Members: 1 representative by each project partner
- Reporting to: European Commission

The General Assembly is the highest-level decision making body of the project. This body is the decision maker as to milestone decisions and will meet at least once a year. It assumes overall responsibility for liaison among partners in relation to the project, for analysing and approving the results, for proper administration and for implementation of the provisions contained in the Grant and Consortium Agreements.

The General Assembly will take decisions related to the following topics:

- Control and steering of the project.
- Modification of the management structure, if required.
- Decision making on strategic issues and conflict resolution.
- Proper implementation of Grant and Consortium Agreements.
- Decisions on proposal of changes on the Consortium/Grant Agreement.
- Monitor overall project progress against objectives and milestones.
- Content, finances and IPRs.
- Assessment and approval of results.
- Approving the management structure and project direction.

- Evolution of the consortium:
 - Entry of a new partner to the consortium and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new partner.
 - Withdrawal of a partner from the consortium and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal.
 - Identification of a breach by a partner of its obligations under the Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement.
 - Declaration of a partner to be a defaulting party.
 - Remedies to be performed by a defaulting party.
 - Termination of a defaulting party's participation in the consortium and measures relating thereto.
 - Proposal to the EC for a change of the Coordinator.
 - Proposal to the EC for suspension of all or part of the Project.
 - Proposal to the EC for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement.

Table 1: General Assembly representatives

Partner	Representative	Email	Proxy	Email
DALMINE	Fabio Praolini	fpraolini@tenaris.com	Manuel Mosconi	mmosconi@tenaris.com
TENOVA	Enrico Malfa	enrico.malfa@tenova.com	Marta Guzzon	marta.guzzon@tenova.com
RINA-CSM	Filippo Cirilli	filippo.cirilli@rina.org	Loredana di Sante	loredana.disante@rina.org
ESTEP	Klaus Peters	Klaus.Peters@estep.eu	Delphine Snaet	d.snaet@estep.eu
K1-MET	Wolfgang Reiter	wolfgang.reiter@k1-met.com	Johannes Rieger	johannes.rieger@k1-met.com
VOESTALPINE	Christoph Thaler	christoph.thaler@voestalpine.com	Tamara Tappeiner	tamara.tappeiner@voestalpine.com

UNIVERSITY OF LEOBEN	Harald Raupenstrauch	harald.raupenstrauch@unileoben.ac.at	Klaus Doschek-Held	Klaus.doschek-held@unileoben.ac.at
FEHS	David Algermisen	d.algermisen@fehs.de	Agnieszka Morillon	a.morillon@fehs.de
THYSSENKRUPP	Nils Jaeger	nils.jaeger@thyssenkrupp.com	Marina do Carmo Carias	marina.do-carmocarias@thyssenkrupp.com
TATA STEEL	Johannes Hage	hans.hage@tatasteel.eu	Jan van der Stel	jan.van-der-stel@tatasteel.eu
CELSA	Anna Domenech	anna.domenech@gcelsa.com	Alexia Boet	alexia.boet@gcelsa.com

2.3 Steering Committee

- Chaired by: DALMINE, represented by Mr. Fabio Praolini.
- Members: 1 representative by each WP leader and project coordinator.
- Reporting to: General Assembly.

The Steering Committee controls/monitors the day-to-day management of the project team, being the main controlling body. The Steering Committee, directed by the Coordinator has the overall responsibility of the project, and this body shall meet twice a year (once, together with the GA) and have conference calls at least every three months.

The following responsibilities belong to the SC:

- Continuous management of the project, ensuring the implementation of the decisions made by the GA.
- First body for the monitoring of the project execution according to the implementation plan.
- Strategic guidance to the project activities and to ensure the relevance of the deliverables.
- Approval of the overall project work plan, budget, reports and financial reports.
- Approval of the implementation plans and associated financial plans.

- Monitoring of the project progress and revision of the achievements.
- Approval of the awareness, dissemination and training plans and its deployment. Agreeing on joint releases and publications.
- Approval of the knowledge management and IPR protection strategy.
- Approval of a Data Management Plan and approval of the appraisal of financial, legal, administrative and technological risks and related contingency plans.
- Approval of networking activities with other EU related projects.
- Manage the WPs and ensure their effective interfacing.
- Identify resource and functional issues to be brought to the attention of the GA (if cannot be solved at the Steering Committee).
- Defining the specifications and boundary conditions of the system to ensure final proper integration.
- To guide and apply corrective measures if some deviation affecting final integration is detected.
- Initiate, coordinate and have organised the WPs.
- Agree on the members of the WP Team, upon a proposal by the Coordinator.

Table 2: Steering Committee representatives

Partner	Representative	Email	Proxy	Email
DALMINE	Fabio Praolini	fpraolini@tenaris.com	Manuel Mosconi	mmosconi@tenaris.com
TENOVA	Marta Guzzon	marta.guzzon@tenova.com	Enrico Malfa	enrico.malfa@tenova.com
RINA-CSM	Loredana di Sante	loredana.disante@rina.org	Filippo Cirilli	filippo.cirilli@rina.org
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VOESTALPINE	Christoph Thaler	christoph.thaler@voestalpine.com	Tamara Tappeiner	tamara.tappeiner@voestalpine.com
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FEHS	Agnieszka Morillon	a.morillon@fehs.de	David Algermissen	d.algermissen@fehs.de
THYSSENKRUPP	Marina do Carmo Carias	marina.do-carmo-carias@thyssenkrupp.com	Nils Jaeger	nils.jaeger@thyssenkrupp.com
TATA STEEL	Johannes Hage	hans.hage@tatasteel.eu	Jan Van Der Stel	jan.van-der-stel@tatasteel.eu
CELSA	Alexia Boet	alexia.boet@gcelsa.com	Anna Domenech	anna.domenech@gcelsa.com

2.4 Working Units: Work Package & Task Leaders

Work Package Leaders (WPL) are responsible for the overall management and coordination at WP level and achievement of the defined results. Each WPL will report periodically to the PC and also to the SC. Moreover, WPL will take the following responsibilities:

- Progress management (assuring all tasks are executed in line with the work program).
- Financial management (periodic evaluation of project expenditure vs. project achievements) in the related WP.
- Project quality management (ensure achievement of technical objectives, assure excellence in execution).
- Review, approve and submit the deliverables from the WP, including technical and periodic reports to the Coordinator.
- Project dissemination.
- Formulate the implementation plan for the activities within the WP for the future period.

- Coordinate on a frequent basis the progress of the technical work under the WP.

Task Leaders (TL) are responsible for the execution and overall coordination of the tasks assigned to them in the implementation plan. TL will have frequent dialogue with the WPL and report periodically to them. In fact, a meeting to explain the strategy to be implemented and the operational plan will be carried out every 6 months, as it is crucial clarifying the activities to be performed during the tasks, as well as the objectives and the documentation to be handled.

2.5 Project Managers

Project Manager (PM) will be Fabio Praolini, who is the Environment Regional Director of Dalmine SpA. He has several years of experience in waste treatment, circular economy and EHS and he is in charge of several research projects for energy saving and waste reduction initiatives.

Technical Manager (TM) of the ReMFra project will be Enrico Malfa, who holds the position of R&D director of TENOVA and is Chairman of Circular Economy Focus Group of ESTEP. K1-MET is in charge of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities. Mr. Wolfgang Reiter, M. Sc. will be the Dissemination and Exploitation Manager. He is Researcher for Metallurgical Process Efficiency and Circularity within K1-MET will also oversee the DMP. The Quality Manager (QM) will be Dr. Agnieszka Morillon, who is a research scientist at FEhS.

3 Communication procedures and tool

ReMFra will make use of several project management tools, with online workspaces, mailing lists, etc. in order to facilitate partners' cooperation, which is the backbone for project success. A professional communication tool, MICROSOFT TEAMS, is also issued for the project, to organize regular conferences to ensure the quality plans and the management procedures set for multi- and bi-lateral contact between partners.

To ensure the proper project execution at management and technical level, it is necessary to establish simple, easy to follow and effective communication flows and methods, guaranteeing that all the information is delivered duly in time to the persons that is needed.

3.1 Management Bodies

Meetings of the governing bodies and technical meetings are specially focused on the monitoring of project progress, achievements review, decision-making and conflict resolution, as well as technical discussion. The responsibility for hosting the meetings will be share between the partners homogeneously.

Meetings of the governing bodies and technical meetings are specially focused on monitoring the overall project progress, achievements revision, decision-making and conflict resolution, as well as technical discussion. The responsibility for hosting the meeting will be shared between partners homogeneously.

As many times as needed during the project, face-to-face or teleconference/videoconference meetings should be organized between:

- Members of the same task.
- Task leaders and WP leader.
- Tasks participants and Task/WP leader.

The meetings of the management bodies are specially focused on monitoring overall project progress and review achievements, milestones and objectives consecution, decision-making on strategic issues and conflict resolution, as well as discussing other issues of interest.

It is highly remarkable the importance of the continuous communication among WPL and TL during the project lifetime. TL will inform WPL about the progress of the corresponding activities under the task, thus the WPL is able to gain a higher-level vision of every activity carried out under the WP. Consequently, WPL will support TL from a higher vision point of view.

The information, agenda, attendants, minutes, presentations, etc. will be uploaded and updated in the project intranet.

3.2 Meetings

Any member of a consortium body:

- should be present or represented at any meeting;
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting;
- shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

The Members of the General Assembly not belonging to the Steering Committee should attend to the Steering Committee meetings when requested in advance by the Project Coordinator.

3.2.1 Preparation and organization of meetings

Convening meetings

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall convene meetings of that Consortium Body.

Hosting of meetings will be rotated among partners. Meetings should be held at the same venue on same/consecutive days when possible. Extraordinary meetings should primarily be teleconferences, provided that this does not hinder the objectives of the meeting.

Notice of a meeting

The chairperson shall give written notice of a meeting to each Partner as soon as possible and no later than 14 calendar days preceding an ordinary meeting and 7 calendar days preceding an extraordinary meeting.

Sending the agenda

The chairperson shall prepare and send each Partner an agenda no later than 14 calendar days preceding the meeting, or 7 calendar days before an extraordinary meeting.

Adding agenda items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Partners must be identified as such on the agenda. Any Partner may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all of the other Members no later than 7 calendar days preceding the meeting and 2 days preceding an extraordinary meeting. During a meeting of the General Assembly the Members present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda. Meetings of the

General Assembly may also be held by tele- or videoconference or other telecommunication means.

Decisions

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the Minutes has been accepted according to Section 6.2.5. of the Consortium Agreement.

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if the Project Coordinator circulates to all Members a written document, which is then agreed by the defined majority (see Section 6.3 of the Consortium Agreement) of all Members Body. Such document shall include the deadline for responses.

Decisions taken without a meeting shall be considered as accepted if, within the period set out in article 6.2.4 of the Consortium Agreement, no Member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson.

The decisions will be binding after the chairperson sends to all Members and to the Project Coordinator a written notification of this acceptance.

Voting rules and quorum

The General Assembly shall not deliberate and decide validly in meetings unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum).

If the quorum is not reached, the Coordinator the General Assembly shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented. Decisions shall be taken by a majority of at least two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast. Blank votes shall not count as votes, but only count to establish if there is a quorum.

Veto rights

A Member that can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of a Consortium Body may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.

When the decision is foreseen on the original agenda, a Member may veto such a decision during the meeting only.

When a decision has been taken on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a Member may veto such decision during the meeting and within 15 calendar days after the draft minutes of the meeting are sent. A Party that is not a Member of a particular Consortium Body may veto a decision within the same number of calendar days after the draft minutes of the meeting are sent.

When a decision has been taken without a meeting a Member may veto such decision within 15 calendar days after written notification by the chairperson of the outcome of the vote.

In case of exercise of veto, the Members of the related Consortium Body shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all its Members.

A Party may neither veto decisions relating to its identification to be in breach of its obligations nor to its identification as a Defaulting Party. The Defaulting Party may not veto decisions relating to its participation and termination in the consortium or the consequences of them.

A Party requesting to leave the consortium may not veto decisions relating thereto

Minutes of the meeting

The chairperson shall produce minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. The chairperson shall send draft minutes to all Members within 10 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from receipt, no Party has sent an objection to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft minutes by written notice. The chairperson shall send the accepted minutes to all the Members, and to the Coordinator, who shall retain copies of them.

3.3 Tools

3.3.1 Project management collaborative space: Microsoft Teams

MICROSOFT TEAMS is the tool that ReMFra project is going to use to support the management.

Below are listed briefly the main applications, among others, of the MICROSOFT TEAMS system:

- File repository
- Contact and mailing list
- Deliverables control
- Planning of tasks and deadlines

- Teleconference system

One of the advantages of using MICROSOFT TEAMS is that you have included in the same tool the videoconference system. Besides the face-to-face meetings, partners will hold as many meetings as necessary through the teleconference system available for the consortium. These meetings could include WP level issues, task level issues, GA or SC meetings; dissemination, etc.

These regular conferences will deal also with the assurance of the quality plans and the management procedures set for multi- and bi-lateral contact between partners.

MICROSOFT TEAMS is a powerful tool, having the following functionalities:

- Multiuser
- Desktop sharing
- Documents sharing
- Chat
- Record of meetings

Other features that MICROSOFT TEAMS has is the possibility to modify documents online, doing easier the collaboration among partners.

3.3.2 Contact lists

In order to support the communication within the consortium a contact list have been uploaded in MICROSOFT TEAMS and distributed among all partners.

When a mail is sent, please include the reference “ReMFra” at the beginning of the subject. An excel file with the distribution list is uploaded

The Project Coordinator should be included in any mail regarding the evolution of the project

4 Quality control

This section deals with the issues related to the general performance and execution of ReMFra and the quality of their work outcome, of which, the PC is responsible for.

The following items are foreseen on each deliverable of the project:

- Cover Page (including the identification of the project and the entities authors)
- Project and document details
- Document history
- Table of contents
- List of figures and tables
- Abbreviations page
- Abstract
- Introductions and objectives
- Methodology / Results / Main analysis...
- Main conclusions
- References (if necessary)
- Annexes, including all detailed technical information (if necessary)

A template of deliverable has been uploaded in the SharePoint, thus all partners use the same structure and format when implementing these documents.

All partners will be involved in the review of deliverables, at least as task participants.

The multi-level management structure will ensure a high degree of quality control from inception through to final completion of the ReMFra project. Progress control will be guaranteed by videoconferences and bilateral discussions between the PC, WP leaders and deliverables responsible.

Draft of the deliverables has to be uploaded in the SharePoint to allow the review by all the partners and in particular the ones involved in the Task. It is important to use the track change for the reviews. At the end of the reviewing process, the PC in accordance with the deliverable responsible upload a pdf version. This will be submitted by PC in the EU Portal.

5 Risk analysis and management

The outcome of the contingency plan will suggest the countermeasures required for preserving the TRL of the project and allowing to achieve results coherent with its original scope.

Description of risk	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Bad communication among partners [Management risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP1	Project Manager will use an inclusive approach in all the consortium meeting and correspondence to ensure proper communication fostering collaboration among partners
A partner leaving the consortium [Management risk] Probability: Low Severity: High	WP1	The consortium is extremely qualified and would share the tasks of the leaving partner among the remaining ones. Alternatively, the consortium would easily find a new partner with partners' large contact network in the steel sector
Wrong estimation of task duration [Management risk] Probability: Medium Severity: Low	WP1	Milestones and deliverables will set the timing and the frequent communications between PM and WP leader will ensure meeting the time schedule proposed
Difficulties in material exchanging among different EU countries due to local legislation constraints [External risk] Probability: Medium Severity: Low	WP2 WP3 WP5	The project partners will act from the very beginning of the project to establish a dialogue with local authorities, for guaranteeing the exchange of material between partners as foreseen in the planned activities
Delay in the procurement of equipment [Technical risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP4	Efforts allocated and Gantt have been designed to avoid possible delays in the deliveries of equipment. Involve in the supply chain EU companies in order to mitigate risk due high volatility in logistic. If necessary, partners together with the coordinator will jointly decide how to modify the Gantt without endangering the further progress of the project. EC will be informed by the coordinator in case a considerable delay to the time schedule is expected.
Delay in the commissioning and start-up of the Plasma Reactor and RecoDust [Technical risk] Probability: Medium Severity: Low		
Delay in the commissioning and start-up of the ReMFra reactors [Technical risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP4 - WP5	Efforts allocated and Gantt diagram have been designed to avoid possible delays. Involved partners together with coordinator will jointly decide how to modify the Gantt chart without endangering the further progress of the project, informing EC accordingly.
Difficulties to reach requirements regarding economic and environmental performance and target product qualities [Technical risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP5	Involved partners will decide on variations in process parameters and, if necessary, the process design (only possible to a certain extent) that can achieve a valid compromise between performance and KPI targets. Further tests at own cost will be performed to optimise the process performance.
Difficulties to convey different feedstock with pneumatic feeding system [Technical risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP5	Pneumatic conveying system is developed for BOF dust. Adoptions of the gas control system if necessary are possible for other feedstock, such as EAF and Hlsarna dust.
Safe and secure storage, sharing and exchange of data [Technical risk]	WP5	All partners involved in the project have a long-lasting experience and all the infrastructures and

Probability: Low Severity: Medium		protocols needed for data collection, storage and exchange, in line with GDPR.
Lack of slag produced through the plasma demo plant [Technical risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP6	If large quantities of slag will not be produced in Task 5.1 (low probability as the device has already been tested on smaller scale), slag that was previously produced in laboratory scale from plasma demo plant will be used for experiments in Task 6.3.
Safety and environmental risks emerging from analyses of the process and use of new products [Technical risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP7	The proved experiences of the ReMFra partners will help to understand driver and barriers, to find opportunities and solution for process modification and increasing of product quality.
Low participation or acceptance from stakeholders or regional parties [Management risk] Probability: Medium Severity: Medium	WP8	ReMFra counts on experienced partners in charge of dissemination activities that would perform corrective actions to encourage the engagement of the stakeholders required for implementation of the demonstrator concept
Poor dissemination to the stakeholders [Management risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP8	Potential stakeholders have been defined comprehensively. A preliminary plan specifying target audience (who?) and the best communication channels (how?) was also set up. Several tasks have been set in the project to ensure stakeholder identification and alignment
Lower level of online interaction (visits) than expected [Management risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP8	Wide dissemination of the URL is planned. Project partners will use different channels to draw visitors to the webpage, including social media, newsletter, etc. Webpage will be promoted at all the events; URL will be included in all communication materials
Low number of participants attend the project's events [Management risk] Probability: Low Severity: Medium	WP8	Partners supporting dissemination events will be communicated early to the target audience. The agenda will be distributed to the target audience at an early stage of event organisation
Low interest of potential customers for the ReMFra process and its secondary products [External risk] Probability: Low Severity: High	WP8	Project consortium will develop improvements of the planned exploitation strategy; project partner ESTEP will use its network to other EC directorates to address a broader spectrum of possible ReMFra customers
Delay of activities, materials delivery and industrial installation due to possible pandemic restrictions [External risk] Probability: Medium Severity: Medium	ALL	All partners are able to work on remote mode in order to continue with all activities that can be carried even under emergency restrictions. An extraordinary meeting of the Steering Committee will decide eventual timing modifications
Increase of energy costs with regard to historic values [External risk] Probability: High Severity: High	WP3 – WP4 – WP5	The extraordinary energy prices will affect the economic feasibility of the project. This will result in reassessment of cost benefit balance. In particular, considering the current energy prices, the erection and the continuous operation of dedicated an industrial demonstrator is not economically viable. The design of the equipment will take into account the new energy prices scenario The duration and magnitude of the testing campaigns will need to be revised accordingly whilst preserving the outcomes of the project without incurring in unbearable costs

<p>Rules for allocation of free EUA for ReMFra activities unclear and/or evolving [External risk] Probability: Medium Severity: Medium</p>	<p>WP5</p>	<p>Given the fact that the costs of EUA is constantly increasing, in case the process will not be considered eligible for receiving free EUA either as new installation or hot metal producer, the operating costs would be significantly higher than foreseen. The Consortium will clarify with the authorities the eligibility of the processes and work with industrial associations (Es. Eurofer) to assure that the revised EU ETS rules will consider new low-carbon production routes as eligible for free EUA. Given the unpredictability of the above countermeasures the duration and the magnitude of the testing activities will need to be reduced while preserving the TRL of the project and its outcomes.</p>
<p>Extraordinary disruption of value chains [External risk] Probability: High Severity: High</p>	<p>WP3 – WP4</p>	<p>During the design phase, the Consortium will evaluate the status of the value chains considering both the costs and the delivery time of equipment and adapt the design, the erection and the operation phases in order to preserve the outcomes of the project.</p>

6 Project reporting

The purpose of the project reporting is for the PC and the EC to review the performance of the project, to be assured of value for money and that the project is on track for successful delivery. It is also for the PC and project manager to follow the technical progresses and use of resources, in order to ensure a smooth deployment of the project and take corrective actions when necessary.

Continuous reporting

The beneficiaries must continuously report on the progress of the action (e.g. deliverables, milestones, outputs/outcomes, critical risks, indicators, etc; if any), in the Portal Continuous Reporting tool and in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out (as agreed with the granting authority).

Standardised deliverables (e.g. progress reports not linked to payments, reports on cumulative expenditure, special reports, etc; if any) must be submitted using the templates published on the Portal.

Periodic reporting

Project partners should thus ensure that their work and effort are fully and correctly reflected in the reports they submit.

The aim of Periodic Reports is for the EC to ensure that project spending is in sync with technical project progress as well as to track scientific, technical and financial progress to the work-plan. The report is officially delivered by the PC to the EC as per the ReMFra Grant Agreement Article 21. In order to submit the periodic report, all partners shall have a financial signatory appointed through the participant portal. The Periodic Report consists of two items: periodic technical report and periodic financial report. Periodic Report will be delivered at M18, M30 and M42.

The technical part includes an overview of the action implementation. It must be prepared using the template available in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool.

The financial part of the additional prefinancing report includes a statement on the use of the previous prefinancing payment.

The financial part of the periodic report includes:

- the financial statements (individual and consolidated; for all beneficiaries/affiliated entities)

- the explanation on the use of resources (or detailed cost reporting table, if required)
- the certificates on the financial statements (CFS) (if required; see Article 24.2 and Data Sheet, Point 4.3).

7 Templates

Word and power point template are uploaded in the sharepoint directory

Conclusion

The basis for the execution of the project due to the procedures included in the deliverable 1.1: Project Handbook were established. This will ensure a coherent and robust management of ReMFra activities.

The Governance Structure of the ReMFra project were defined, explaining all the execution bodies. Moreover, the main contact and the proxy of each partner for the General Assembly and Steering Committee were defined. The communication procedures and the tools for a smooth management of the project were explained.

The criteria and general characteristics of the quality control were showed in this deliverable. This procedure will help Consortium to avoid delays in the submission of deliverables to the participant portal and the achievement of the milestones.

Finally, the project reporting procedures, the legal and financial aspects, the templates and patters of the project and the useful links were explained.

This document might be update during the execution of the project if the activities modifies some point or the partners make some substantial change.

This document has to be intended as support to the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, Project Handbook cannot substitute these Agreements.

Appendix I – Deliverables, Milestones and GANTT

LIST OF DELIVERABLES and MILESTONE

Deliverables ReMFra											Starting date	01/12/2022
Deliverables												
Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status	
WP1	D1.1	Project Handbook	An internal document collecting all the necessary guidelines and instruction to ensure the positive outcome of the project	DALMINE	R	PU	01-apr-23				Pending	
WP1	D1.2	Data Management	Documentation necessary to manage the data and research outputs	K1-MET	Other	PU	01-giu-23				Pending	
WP1	D1.3	Updated Data Management	Update of DMP	K1-MET	Other	PU	01-apr-26				Pending	
WP2	D2.1	Material and process	Report detailing the requirements of the Plasma reactor process both in terms of inputs and operational parameters	CSM	R	PU	01-ago-23				Pending	
WP2	D2.2	Material and process	Report detailing the requirements of the RecoDust process both in terms of inputs and operational parameters	VAS	R	PU	01-ago-23				Pending	
WP2	D2.3	Fulfilled legal requirements	Guidelines and permitting required to import dusts to Austria from other EU countries	TENOVA	R	PU	01-ago-23				Pending	
WP3	D3.1	Material pre-process	Report dealing with feedstock pre processing of ReMFra process	CSM SPA	SEN	PU	01-mar-24				Pending	
WP3	D3.2	Design of Plasma reactor	Report with engineer of ReMFra application (including layouts, connections, utilities, etc.)	TENOVA	R	PU	01-mar-24				Pending	
WP3	D3.3	Evaluation of overall process	Detailed document of the ReMFra processes that will be part of WIP5	TENOVA	R	PU	01-mar-24				Pending	
WP4	D4.1	Plasma reactor	Installation of plasma reactor at Dalmine site	DALMINE	DEM	PU	01-feb-24				Pending	
WP4	D4.2	Plasma reactor	Verification of the quality of the components, erection and certifications of Plasma reactor	DALMINE	R	PU	01-feb-25				Pending	
WP4	D4.3	RecoDust verification	Verification of the quality of the components, adaptation and certifications of Plasma reactor	K1-MET	R	PU	01-feb-24				Pending	
WP4	D4.4	Process sequence	Schedule of the RecoDust trials	K1-MET	R	PU	01-mar-24				Pending	
WP5	D5.1	Plasma demo operation	Report of Plasma reactor trials in Dalmine site with product analysis	DALMINE	R	PU	01-gen-26				Pending	
WP5	D5.2	RecoDust demo operation	Report of RecoDust trials with products analysis	K1-MET	R	PU	01-mar-26				Pending	
WP5	D5.3	Feasibility study	Evaluation of ReMFra approach for TATA dusts in RecoDust process	TATA	R	PU	01-mar-26				Pending	
WP5	D5.4	Feasibility study	Evaluation of ReMFra approach for TKSE residues	TKSE	R	PU	01-mar-26				Pending	
WP5	D5.5	Feasibility study	Evaluation of ReMFra approach for Celisa case based on residues characterization	CELISA	R	PU	01-mar-26				Pending	
WP5	D5.6	Feasibility study	Evaluation of ReMFra approach for Tenaris Dalmine case based on residues characterization and tests	DALMINE	R	PU	01-mar-26				Pending	
WP6	D6.1	Description of ReMFra	KPIs definition and descriptions & CO2 and energy reduction baseline description	K1-MET	R	PU	01-apr-23				Pending	
WP6	D6.2	Mid-term KPI evaluation	Update of KPIs & further analysis on CO2 and energy reduction and other impacts	K1-MET	R	PU	01-sei-24				Pending	
WP6	D6.3	Final ReMFra Key Performance Indicators	Update of KPIs and conclusive analysis on CO2 and energy reduction (and other impacts)	K1-MET	R	PU	01-apr-26				Pending	
WP6	D6.4	Analysis of certified products	Guidelines to certify the Plasma slag	FENS	R	PU	01-giu-26				Pending	
WP7	D7.1	LCA for ReMFra	LCA studies for ReMFra	CSM SPA	R	PU	01-giu-26				Pending	
WP7	D7.2	LCC for ReMFra	LCC studies for ReMFra	CSM SPA	R	PU	01-giu-26				Pending	
WP7	D7.3	Best practices for ReMFra	Guidelines, protocols and procedures in terms of Health and Safety issued, ecc	CSM SPA	R	PU	01-giu-26				Pending	
WP8	D8.1	DEC Plan	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy including target audiences, channels, visualisations, website	K1-MET	R	PU	01-apr-23				Pending	
WP8	D8.2	Project webpage	Project webpage online	DALMINE	DEC	PU	01-giu-23				Pending	
WP8	D8.3	Replication potential	Replication potential report based on stakeholders' identification and engagement	K1-MET	R	PU	01-giu-24				Pending	
WP8	D8.4	Report on context	Report for all the dissemination and communications activities. It will be updated each six months from M18	K1-MET	R	PU	01-giu-26				Pending	
WP8	D8.5	ReMFra market	Detailed study on market analysis of ReMFra approach	TENOVA	R	PU	01-giu-26				Pending	
WP8	D8.6	ReMFra business plan	Business plan of ReMFra	TENOVA	R	PU	01-giu-26				Pending	
WP8	D8.7	Preliminary ReMFra business plan	Preliminary business plan of ReMFra. This will be fed by trials results ensuring proper incorporation of financial, market	TENOVA	R	PU	01-giu-24				Pending	

Milestones ReMFra

Milestones											Starting date	01/12/2022
Work Package No	Milestone Related No	Milestone Name	Means of verification	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status			
WP1	1	Kick off meeting	Project started, all partners aligned on project objectives, activities and roles	DALMINE	01-apr-23				Done			
WP1-WP8	2	Data Management	Data Management Plan and Dissemination and Communication Plan	K1-MET	01-giu-23				Pending			
WP2	3	Definition of use cases	Targeted residues properly classified, Plasma reactor	CSM	01-ago-23				Pending			
WP3	4	Specification for process	Basic and detailed design of Plasma Reactor and RecoDust	TENOVA	01-mar-24				Pending			
WP8	5	5th newsletter published	5th newsletter sent to the distribution list	K1-MET	01-ago-24				Pending			
WP5	6	RecoDust demo operation	RecoDust ready for ramp up	VAS	01-set-24				Pending			
WP6	7	Mid-term KPI evaluation	Project KPIs updated	K1-MET	01-ott-24				Pending			
WP6	8	First laboratory analysis	First sample received at FEHS premises and start of analysis	FENS	01-apr-25				Pending			
WP5	9	End of specific demonstration	End of preliminary test (specific daily tests) with all the feedstocks	DALMINE	01-mag-25				Pending			
WP7	10	LCI inventory definition	Life Cycle Inventory defined as first step of the LCA	CSM	01-giu-25				Pending			
WP5	11	Residues delivery	All the residues from TATA, TKSE and CELISA delivered	TKSE	01-set-25				Pending			
WP6	12	Final KPIs update	Final Key Performance Indicators assessment	DALMINE	01-apr-26				Pending			
WP4	13	Plasma demo operation	Plasma reactor ready for preliminary tests	K1-MET	01-feb-25				Pending			

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